

A HYBRID STRATEGIC PROBABILISTIC FRAMEWORK FOR FUNCTIONAL ASSESSMENT AND RISK CONTROL IN INDUSTRIAL SYSTEMS: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT: This study proposes a strategic management methodology for evaluating risk variables in industrial systems through the development of a hybrid decision-support dashboard. The framework integrates the Balanced Scorecard (BSC), the OFAI method (Objectives, Key Success Factors, Actions, Indicators), and Bayesian Networks (BN), with the addition of a fifth axis that focuses on environmental factors. A review of existing literature highlights the lack of integrated approaches that combine probabilistic reasoning with strategic performance frameworks, underlining the novelty and scientific relevance of this contribution. The methodology is validated through a real-world case study in a textile manufacturing company. Using expert knowledge and historical data, the Bayesian model allows for the simulation of various risk scenarios. Results indicate a notable improvement in profitability and key performance indicators under optimized strategic scenarios. These findings validate the model's ability to support risk-informed decision-making and strategic adaptability in complex, dynamic industrial environments.

KEYWORDS: Risk assessment, manufacturing systems, OFAI method, Balanced Scorecard (BSC), Bayesian Network (BN).

1 INTRODUCTION

Industrial failures caused by inadequate risk management result in significant annual losses and threaten the sustainability of complex manufacturing systems [1,2]. In today's volatile and uncertain environment, organizations need integrated strategic frameworks that combine thorough functional evaluation with dynamic risk control to support effective decision-making and sustain competitive advantage. The growing complexity of modern industrial systems, alongside rapid technological changes and intense global competition, challenges traditional performance management tools, which often lack sufficient detail and flexibility [3,4]. The Balanced Scorecard (BSC), developed by Kaplan and Norton [5–7], remains a widely adopted strategic framework linking operational activities to organizational objectives through balanced financial and non-financial indicators, both in the private sector [8] and in the public sector [9]. In particular, the classical BSC shows significant limitations when

applied to dynamic, high-risk industrial environments. Its static nature and limited capacity to address uncertainty and rapid change often result in costly failures, operational delays, increased expenses, and reduced responsiveness factors that ultimately compromise system sustainability [10–13]. Therefore, there is a pressing need to go beyond traditional static frameworks and adopt integrated, probabilistic strategic models that enhance performance evaluation while anticipating and managing risks effectively. The key challenge lies in reconciling operational accuracy with uncertainty management to optimize industrial decision-making and minimize disruption-related costs.

To address this challenge, this study incorporates the OFAI method (Objectives, Key Success Factors, Actions, and Indicators) into the BSC framework. The OFAI method is a structured performance management approach, particularly well-suited for evaluating information systems (IS). This approach enhances the alignment between strategic goals and daily execution [14], where it is highlighted as a

valuable tool for improving the coherence and efficiency of performance measurement in complex environments like information systems.

Recent studies emphasize the need to evolve the BSC by embedding agility, sustainability, and technological adaptability, as demonstrated by its alignment with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals [15,16]. Additionally, integrating strategic risk profiles into BSC models has proven to improve managerial decision-making [17].

Meanwhile, rapid technological advances, particularly digitalization and AI-driven innovation, are reshaping performance management by enabling more agile, data-driven approaches [18]. Bayesian Networks (BNs) stand out as powerful probabilistic tools that model uncertainty and causal relationships, supporting informed decision-making in complex industrial systems [19,20]. Their ability to dynamically update beliefs based on new information makes them especially suited for risk assessment in volatile contexts. However, integrated approaches combining the BSC with probabilistic risk modeling remain relatively rare.

In response, this study proposes an innovative hybrid framework that combines the Balanced Scorecard, OFAI, and Bayesian Networks. A key innovation of this study is the explicit addition of a fifth perspective dedicated to environmental performance within the BSC-OFAI-BN framework. This original contribution responds to emerging industrial needs and is not yet addressed in current BSC implementations. While previous studies [21,22] have highlighted the importance of environmental sustainability, few have structurally integrated it as a dedicated BSC perspective. By combining these methodologies, the framework equips managers with the ability to evaluate performance across financial, operational, and environmental dimensions while anticipating and mitigating risks through probabilistic inference. This integrated approach fosters informed decision-making, enhances organizational agility, and supports sustainable development in industrial systems.

The practical relevance and effectiveness of this framework are demonstrated through an empirical case study in a wool-spinning workshop within the textile sector, an industry known for its complex risk management challenges and evolving sustainability requirements. The results confirm that the framework facilitates strategic alignment, proactive risk management, and strengthened organizational resilience. Furthermore, its modular design supports gradual integration into existing management

systems, making it a pragmatic and innovative solution to contemporary industrial challenges.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the proposed hybrid methodology; Section 3 details the industrial case study; Section 4 discusses the results; and Section 5 concludes with directions for future research.

2 METHODOLOGY

The development of strategic dashboards is a critical step in translating high-level objectives into actionable and measurable insights. In management science, two primary schools of thought shape the design of these tools. The first, known as the "methodological" or French approach, builds indicators by systematically deriving them from strategic objectives. Notable frameworks in this tradition include OVAR (Objectives, Action Variables, Responsibilities) and OFAI (Objectives, Key Success Factors, Actions, Indicators).

In contrast, the model-driven or "American" approach emphasizes the identification of operational variables that act as strategic levers. This approach seeks to align operational activity with long-term goals through the use of key indicators. Prominent examples include the SKANDIA navigator and the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) [14]. Despite their cultural distinctions, both approaches ultimately converge on enhancing performance and strategic alignment.

It is now widely acknowledged that no single method is universally superior. Tools must be adapted to organizational needs and contextual realities. In this work, we propose a hybrid methodology that addresses several core principles:

- A forward-looking and integrated strategic vision
- Consideration of technological, human, and organizational risks
- Identification of key success factors that drive performance
- Analysis of adverse events and vulnerabilities
- Control of risks through both awareness and proactive management

To meet these challenges, we introduce a hybrid model that integrates the strategic scope of the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) with the structured framework of the OFAI method. The BSC ensures high-level strategic coherence across multiple performance dimensions, while the OFAI method facilitates hierarchical decomposition from strategic goals to measurable indicators and actionable initiatives. To this hybrid core, we add an environmental dimension to address sustainability and long-term operational resilience. Additionally,

the integration of Bayesian inference brings a dynamic, data-driven component to the model. Bayesian Networks allow for continuous learning, inference under uncertainty, and the probabilistic updating of system states based on real-time data and expert knowledge.

The resulting BSC/OFAI/BN framework aggregates essential performance indicators, offers a holistic view of operations, enables early detection of disruptions, and supports adaptive, real-time strategic decision-making. The comprehensive nature of this framework makes it a valuable decision-support tool across industrial contexts.

The methodology is illustrated in Fig. 1, highlighting the conceptual integration of strategic planning, operational execution, and probabilistic reasoning.

Fig. 1. Proposed approach

2.1 The Balanced Scorecard (BSC) approach

The Balanced Scorecard (BSC) extends beyond the role of a conventional dashboard. It is not merely a decision-support or performance-monitoring tool but a comprehensive strategic management framework. It enables organizations to evaluate present performance while aligning their operations with long-term strategic goals through a multi-perspective approach.

Kaplan and Norton [5] emphasized that in increasingly complex and dynamic environments, organizations must possess a clear understanding of their objectives and the pathways to achieve them to ensure sustainable success. According to their model (Fig. 2), the BSC assesses performance through four interdependent perspectives: (1) Financial, (2) Customer, (3) Internal Processes, and (4) Learning and Growth.

The Learning and Growth perspective lays the foundation for internal development. It emphasizes innovation, employee training, and organizational capacity-building elements essential for driving continuous improvement. The Internal Processes perspective focuses on optimizing key operations to ensure quality and efficiency. The Customer perspective reflects the organization's ability to satisfy and retain its clients. Ultimately, the Financial perspective consolidates the results from the other three, serving as an indicator of overall value creation and shareholder satisfaction.

These four perspectives are causally interlinked, forming a logical and strategic hierarchy. The use of strategic maps to visualize interrelationships between performance dimensions—highlighting how progress in one area can drive improvements in others—was proposed as a key enhancement to the Balanced Scorecard [6,23]. This systemic view positions the BSC as a powerful instrument for aligning daily operations with long-term strategy.

Fig. 2. The 4 axes of the BSC [6]

2.2 OFAI method

The OFAI method (Objectives, Key Success Factors, Actions, Indicators) enhances the foundational OVAR model by adding an essential layer of analysis: the identification of key success factors. While the OVAR method links actions directly to objectives, OFAI introduces intermediate

elements of success factors that reflect the internal strengths and capabilities critical to achieving strategic goals. These factors serve as the foundation for defining relevant actions and measurable performance indicators [14].

The OFAI framework proceeds in a structured manner: beginning with the articulation of strategic objectives, it identifies the key success factors, which are then used to develop corresponding actions and define meaningful indicators. This logical and hierarchical decomposition ensures a more substantial alignment between strategic vision and operational execution. It also facilitates traceability, transparency, and consistency in performance evaluation across organizational levels.

As shown in Table 1, the OFAI method can be effectively applied to objectives such as increasing a company’s profit margin by 10%. Each component objective, success factors, actions, and indicators are mapped, illustrating the method’s coherence, practicality, and potential for real-world implementation.

Tab. 1. Example of variation of the OFAI method

Objectives	Key factors of success	Actions	Indicators
Increase margins by 10%	The sales	Decrease rebates	Percentage discount /Capital
		Increase the amount of sales	Percentage of contracts with all offers
		Increase sales volume	Order amount / customer
	Purchases	Better buy raw materials	Purchase price / standard price
		Better manage the stock	Number of new products tested
		Look for material savings	Full cost for a unit sold
	Productive performance	Control production costs	Cost of the package sent
		Controlled logistics costs	Cost per order placed
		Control commercial costs	Cost of acquiring a new customer

2.3 Bayesian Network (NB)

Bayesian Networks (BNs) are graphical probabilistic models widely used to manage uncertainty in complex systems [24]. They represent variables as nodes and their causal or conditional relationships as directed edges in a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) [25]. Each node is associated with either prior or conditional probabilities, allowing for the joint probability distribution to be factorized as:

$$P(X) = \prod_{i=1}^n P(X_i/\text{parents}(X_i)) \quad (1)$$

BNs support reasoning under uncertainty by updating beliefs using Bayes’ theorem. This enables both predictive analysis (e.g., P(effect /cause)) and diagnostic rationale (e.g., P(cause /effect)) [26].

In this work, BNs are used to model dependencies among performance indicators. Probabilities are defined using expert inputs and historical data, and inference is performed to assess risk, support decisions, and simulate scenarios.

BNs offer an adaptive, data-driven approach and have become essential in AI for capturing uncertain knowledge in industrial systems [27, 28].

3 CASE STUDY: APPLICATION IN A TEXTILE COMPANY

The proposed hybrid framework was implemented in a combed spinning workshop within a textile company. This workshop specializes in eliminating short fibers to produce more uniform and higher-quality yarn. Unlike carded spinning, the process includes additional stages such as preparatory drafting, doubling, combing, assembling, and twisting, each introducing specific operational challenges.

3.1 Strategic Dashboard Implementation

Based on the proposed hybrid methodology, a strategic dashboard was developed for the target textile company (Table 2). This dashboard aims to identify key objectives and success factors across each of the company’s strategic axes: Financial, Customer, Internal Process, Learning, and Environment, while also defining relevant indicators and associated actions. Its purpose is to support informed decision-making at all organizational levels, reduce operational risks, and enhance system performance.

Rather than providing an exhaustive operational overview, the dashboard is focused on the most critical objectives aligned with strategic priorities. Through the integration of the BSC and OFAI approaches, the model highlights the key success factors and risk-related indicators relevant to

industrial operations. Once these indicators are identified, risk control becomes more structured and reliable.

After constructing the dashboard, we proceeded to establish integration links between the strategic axes. These connections enable the identification of interdependencies among organizational functions and provide a foundation for causal modeling and decision-making (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Causal links

3.2 BN-Based Inference and Risk Simulation

To enhance the dashboard’s dynamic capabilities and manage uncertainty, Bayesian Networks (BNs) were integrated into the model. The causal graph, derived from strategic links within the dashboard, was used as the foundation for constructing the BN (Fig. 5). The implementation followed a two-phase approach:

- Graphical Mapping:** The causal structure was translated into a Bayesian Network using BayesiaLab software. Root nodes represented primary indicators, intermediate nodes captured interactions between axes, and leaf nodes represented outcomes (Fig. 4). The structure reflected the dependencies visualized in the strategic graph (Fig. 3).

- Numerical Mapping:** Initial probabilities were defined for root nodes using expert input and historical data (Tab. 3). Conditional Probability Tables (CPTs) were established for intermediate and leaf nodes, using logical scenarios and calculations derived through Bayes’ theorem. This mapping process is formally represented by equation (2), which defines the probabilistic propagation from causes to effects across the network.

$$p(A) = \sum_{i \in I} p(A|B_i)p(B_i) \quad (2)$$

This equation represents the marginal probability of A, calculated by summing over all possible conditional probabilities of A given B_i, weighted by the prior probabilities of B_i. It underpins Bayesian inference used for updating beliefs based on observed evidence.

Fig. 4. Proposed Mapping Causal links to BN

Tab. 2. The textile company dashboard

Strategic targets	Key factors of success	Actions	Indicators	The objective of the company
Financial axis Improve productivity and reduce costs	Management control	Evaluate the profitability of the business.	- CRR cost reduction rate - Turnover growth rate TR - Profit economy *	$CRR = \frac{\text{turnover of year X}}{\text{turnover of year (X-1)}} \cdot \text{It must be } > 1.$ $TR = \frac{\text{costs for year X}}{\text{costs for year (X-1)}} \cdot \text{It must be } < 1.$
Customer axis Improved satisfaction customer	The sales (Time limit)	Reduce the average order processing times	-Customer satisfaction	$\text{Satisfaction index (min 80\%)} = \frac{\text{number of satisfied customers}}{\text{total number of customers}}$
Process axis Ensure the proper functioning of the manufacturing process as well as in terms of quality.	The production	Strengthen production capacities	- Realization rate (RR) - Order delivered on time	$RR = \frac{\text{realized production capacity}}{\text{benchmark production capacity}}$ The goal is to maximize the RR to more than 90%. - Four times a month minimum.
Learning axis - Job satisfaction - More staff evaluation - Manage skills and knowledge	Technology, human and management resource	-Improve technological and human capacity - Innovation - share knowledge	- Training costs compared to turnover - Average age of equipment - Staff responsibility *	- Training costs in relation to turnover (desired value 3%) - The equipment has been recently renovated
Environment axis Prevent environmental risk and pollution	Working environment	Use potential capacities	-Environment (micro-organism) *	In this case, the source of danger is associated with microorganisms (Covid-19 virus).

* The indicators proposed for the textile company

Fig. 5. BN for the textile company

3.3 Strategic Dashboard Implementation

The BN facilitated real-time probabilistic inference. It enabled the prediction of how specific inputs, such as increased training or reduced delivery times, could influence performance indicators like profit. Figures 6 and 7 illustrate examples of CPT formulation and their application within the model.

Through inference, the system could assess the current state and simulate alternative scenarios by updating beliefs when evidence is observed (Fig. 8). This capability supports both predictive and diagnostic analyses.

Notably, the BN addressed gaps associated with missing or uncertain data. For example, the environmental axis considered contamination risks such as COVID-19. The BN automatically adjusted dependent variables in response to assumptions set on environmental or operational inputs, demonstrating its adaptability. Simulations shown in Figures 9, 10, and 11 highlight how key indicators such as process performance, learning (e.g., staff responsibility and training costs), and environmental conditions influence financial outcomes. Figure 10, in particular, illustrates the influence of learning indicators on profit, demonstrating the model's diagnostic precision.

The effectiveness of the BN-based integration is further demonstrated through simulation outcomes and strategic interpretation, as detailed in the following section (Section 4, including Figures 9 to 11).

Tab. 3. Prior probabilities

Events	Probability %	
	Bad	Good
Average age of equipment	20	80
Responsibility of personnel	49,862	50,138
Training costs compared to turnover	47	53
Environnement	30	70

Distribution de probabilités		Propriétés	
Realization...	Order deliv...	Bad	Good
Bad	Bad	100,000	0,000
Bad	Good	100,000	0,000
Good	Bad	100,000	0,000
Good	Good	0,000	100,000

Fig. 6. Table of prior probabilities, on BayésiaLab

Distribution de probabilités		Propriétés	
		Bad	Good
		47,000	53,000

Fig. 7. Conditional probability table, on BayésiaLab

Fig 8. Inference with BayésiaLab, for the current state of the company

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the key findings derived from the implementation of the proposed hybrid evaluation model and discusses their strategic implications. The integration of the Balanced Scorecard (BSC), the OFAI method, and Bayesian Networks (BN) highlights significant potential for risk identification and strategic performance monitoring, particularly in the textile manufacturing sector.

The enhanced BSC framework, now enriched with the OFAI method, allows for the systematic extraction of strategic indicators directly from key success factors. This ensures a more precise alignment between organizational objectives and measurable metrics, facilitating the faster and more reliable detection of risks. Additionally, the incorporation of Bayesian Networks strengthens the model by enabling probabilistic reasoning and real-time inference, which is critical in dynamic and uncertain environments.

Initial Inference and Strategic Insights

Initial inference results, shown in Fig. 8, indicated that the baseline probability of achieving profitability at the core financial target was 63.16%. While this figure provides a solid starting point, it underscores the necessity for targeted strategic improvements to enhance economic performance. These results suggest that while the system is performing adequately, significant opportunities for growth remain.

Simulation Scenarios and Sensitivity Analysis

To assess the impact of key performance drivers, several simulation scenarios were performed, offering critical insights into strategic levers influencing profitability.

When the realization rate within the Internal Process axis was set to 100% (Fig. 9), profitability surged from 63.16% to 93.18%, marking an increase of 30.02 percentage points. This demonstrates the critical importance of optimizing internal processes such as production efficiency and quality control for driving financial success.

Similarly, adjustments to two Learning and Growth indicators, staff responsibility and training investment, resulted in an increase in the probability of achieving profitability from 63.16% to 84.38%, representing a gain of 21.22 percentage points (Fig. 10). This emphasizes the importance of investing in human capital development, employee engagement, and training as fundamental drivers of organizational performance.

The Environmental axis also emerged as a key factor. When environmental safety was set to 100%, simulating a disruption-free scenario (e.g., the absence of COVID-19 or other external crises),

profitability improved from 63.16% to 71.55%, corresponding to an increase of 8.39 percentage points (Fig. 11). This highlights the crucial role of external stability in ensuring continuous and profitable operations.

4.1 Dynamic Adaptability and Real-Time Decision Support

A key feature of the proposed model is its ability to dynamically recalculate intermediate and outcome indicators in response to changes in root variables. This adaptability distinguishes it from traditional dashboards, which typically rely on manual updates and lack flexibility under uncertainty. By incorporating Bayesian inference, the BN model ensures real-time adaptation, providing continuous decision support even in the presence of incomplete or ambiguous data. This capability allows organizations to make better-informed, timely decisions in complex, fast-evolving environments.

4.2 The Inclusion of Environmental Factors: A Conceptual Advancement

The introduction of the **Environmental** axis within the BSC framework represents a significant conceptual advancement. This fifth axis enables the model to account for external risk factors such as pandemics, regulatory changes, or natural disasters that can profoundly impact organizational outcomes. Simulation results validate the critical role of environmental factors in shaping organizational performance. By incorporating these external variables, the framework provides a more comprehensive and proactive approach to strategic planning, enhancing both long-term resilience and sustainability.

This broader perspective allows organizations to anticipate better and navigate external challenges, ensuring more resilient decision-making in the face of uncertainty. As industries increasingly face external shocks, such as health crises or regulatory pressures, this expanded BSC framework becomes indispensable for safeguarding organizational continuity and promoting sustainable success.

4.3 Forward-Looking Decision Support for Resilience and Sustainability

These findings highlight the value of the proposed hybrid model in facilitating forward-looking decision-making, particularly in environments characterized by uncertainty and rapid change. The model's comprehensive approach, which integrates internal, external, and probabilistic factors, equips organizations to manage risks, optimize performance, and strengthen resilience proactively. By incorporating key success factors, environmental considerations, and real-time Bayesian inference, the

framework ensures that organizations are better prepared to navigate the complexities of the modern industrial landscape.

In conclusion, the model provides a robust and dynamic tool for strategic risk management, ensuring that decision-makers are equipped with the insights needed to drive performance while adapting to the constantly changing conditions of the industrial sector.

Fig. 9. Bayesian inference to set the indicator “Realization rate” at 100%

Fig. 10. Bayesian inference to set the learning axis indicator to 100%

Fig. 11. Bayesian inference to set the “Environment” indicator to 100%

5 CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVE

In the face of growing uncertainty and complexity in industrial ecosystems, organizations require decision-making tools that are not only integrated but also intelligent and adaptive. This study introduced a hybrid strategic evaluation framework designed to address these challenges by integrating the Balanced Scorecard (BSC), the OFAI method, and Bayesian Networks (BNs).

The proposed model advances the conventional BSC by incorporating a fifth strategic axis of environmental performance, allowing organizations to account for external disruptions and sustainability challenges. The OFAI method strengthens this framework by systematically identifying critical success factors, while BNs provide the inferential power to perform dynamic risk evaluations and scenario simulations in real-time.

The application of this hybrid framework to a textile manufacturing case confirmed its practical relevance and diagnostic strength. Key findings revealed that enhancing internal process realization and learning-related factors (e.g., training and responsibility) had a significant positive impact on financial performance. The environmental axis proved equally crucial in addressing external threats, such as COVID-19, which would otherwise remain outside the scope of traditional BSC models.

By enabling automatic updates and probabilistic reasoning, the model goes beyond static dashboards and supports continuous, adaptive decision-making.

This positions it as a valuable tool for strategic risk management in data-driven industries.

Looking forward, this framework offers promising avenues for future development. Integration with IoT technologies and real-time data acquisition could facilitate applications in predictive maintenance, supply chain risk assessment, and operational resilience. Furthermore, coupling the model with advanced analytics and machine learning algorithms would enhance its predictive capacity and operational intelligence.

Notably, the approach aligns with the principles of Industry 5.0, which prioritize human-centricity, sustainability, and system resilience. By embedding human and environmental dimensions within a probabilistic and intelligent framework, the model lays a foundation for more responsive and socially responsible industrial strategies.

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